

Exchange Behavior of Soil Organic Matter

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The equilibrium constants of exchange reaction in soil organic matter have been determined by means of the membrane electrodes. Humic acids and humates have been isolated from Dehradun and Assam soils.

The equilibria have been investigated :

If K_F and K_B are equilibrium constants for forward and backward reactions it has been found that $K_F \neq 1/K_B$ which is due to hysteresis.

Attempts were made by Waksman, Tyurin and Bremner¹ to outline the historical development of the chemical investigation of humus. Published data extending over many years on the physicochemical properties of humic substances are difficult to correlate. The truly acidic properties of humic acid was established by means of electrochemical measurements².

Detailed study of exchange properties of humic matter made by Zadmard³ and Schachtschabel⁴, had firmly established the importance of exchange properties of humic matter and soil fertility.

According to Mattson⁵ the fertility is due to the high exchange capacity of humic matter present in the soil, which controls the fertility of soil through Donnan equilibria.

The colloidal properties of humic substances were known in the early history of Soil Science and were studied during the development of Colloid chemistry. General acceptance of humates as a colloidal transporting agent has become difficult in the light of more recent advances in Co-ordination chemistry. Our knowledge about the mechanism of fixation or bonding between the metal and organic constituents involved is very poor. Lingong and Bisque⁶ proposed two types of mechanism; (i) the metal can form metal-organic colloids and (ii) the metal can form metal-organic complexes.

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Broadbent and Ott⁷ suggested that retention of polyvalent cations by soil organic matter is in part due to the formation of complexes, some of which may be chelates, although simple salt formation with—COOH is also involved. Cation retention by soil organic matter is influenced by the valency of the cations. Again among the cations of the same valency, the cations which form chelates are retained to a greater extent. Electrochemical behaviour of soil organic matter has been studied by ion activities measurement by membrane electrode⁸.

A quantitative study of cation exchange capacity involves the measurement of activities rather than concentrations. Mclean⁹ *et al.* membrane technique may be used for ion activity measurements. The law of mass action has been found suitable in the study of ion exchange phenomena of soil organic matter. The expressions for selectivity co-efficient or equilibrium constants of exchange reactions are similar to clay systems¹⁰.

EXPERIMENTAL

For the present investigation, organic matter from two samples of Dehradun soil and that from Assam soil have been used. Isolation and purification of humic acid have been done by the usual methods. The c.e.c. has been determined potentiometrically by titration with NaOH. Humic acids have been then converted into Ba- and Ca-humates by adding the corresponding chlorides in alkaline solution and then freeing the suspensions from electrolytes in the centrifuge and finally by mild dialysis.

To study the exchange reaction equal volumes of humic acids and humates are taken in 50 ml corning flask and increasing amounts of electrolytes have been added and water added to make up the volume to such a value that the colloid content is the same in each

TABLE IA

EMF's (mv) read against $a_{Ca} = 0.0027$	Humate phase			Solution phase			
	$a_H \times 10^5$	$a_{Ca} \times 10^5$	EMF (mv) $a_{Ca} = 0.0027$	$a_H \times 10^4$	$a_{Ca} \times 10^4$	K	1/k
35.5	7.08	7.18	20.0	2.63	3.99	2.48	0.40
42.0	6.31	6.02	16.5	3.02	5.34	2.58	0.38
48.0	4.90	3.10	13.0	2.51	8.07	1.00	0.99
49.0	4.78	2.70	11.0	3.16	9.23	1.28	0.78
38.0	6.16	9.97	7.0	3.09	13.46	1.86	0.53
42.0	6.16	6.13	5.5	3.02	15.44	0.95	1.04

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bottle. The contents have been kept, with occasional shaking for five to seven days, at room temperature i.e., 30°, for the attainment of equilibrium. The colloidal portions have been centrifuged and then redepended in the same volume of water. Ion activities in both the solution and the colloidal phases have been measured with membrane electrodes using the respective reference solutions.

TABLE IB

JSP

Colloid Content = 0.067

Membrane used—MC-3142 and $U_H/U_{Ca} = 1.5$
 2 Humic Acid + $CaCl_2 \rightarrow Ca-(Humate)_2 + 2HCl$.

Humate phase			Solution phase			K
EMF (mv)	$a_H \times 10^9$	$a_{Ca} \times 10^5$	EMF (mv)	$a_H \times 10^9$	$a_{Ca} \times 10^4$	
32	1.00	20.14	16	0.758	7.90	6.82
38	1.00	14.60	11	1.00	11.60	7.94
49	1.202	6.28	10	1.04	12.53	2.66
40	0.794	12.51	6	1.41	17.03	4.31
40	1.122	12.51	5	1.99	18.40	4.67
38	1.445	14.60	1.0	2.45	25.00	5.95

TABLE IIA

JSP

Colloid Content = 0.06%

Membrane used—MC-3142 and $U_H/U_{Ba} = 1.0\%$
 2Humic Acid + $BaCl_2 \rightarrow Ba(Humate)_2 + 2HCl$.

EMF (mv)	$a_H \times 10^5$	$a_{Ba} \times 10^5$	EMF (mv)	$a_H \times 10^4$	$a_{Ba} \times 10^4$	K	1/k
49	5.25	3.66	17	3.80	5.46	3.51	0.28
51	4.89	2.94	15	3.89	6.58	2.82	0.35
45	5.01	6.03	13	3.63	8.14	3.88	0.26
46	4.07	4.38	11	4.46	9.37	4.57	0.22
49	4.46	4.05	11	4.17	9.57	3.70	0.27
48	4.17	4.69	10	4.17	9.94	4.72	0.21

TABLE IIB

 $U_H/U_{Ba} = 1.5$

$Ba-(Humate)_2 + 2HCl \rightarrow 2Humic Acid + BaCl_2$
 E.M.F's measured against $a_{Ca} = 0.0027$.

Humate phase			Solution phase			K
EMF (mv)	$a_H \times 10^5$	$a_{Ba} \times 10^5$	EMF (mv)	$a_H \times 10^4$	$a_{Ba} \times 10^4$	
47	0.022	7.30	26	0.017	3.66	0.079
50	0.251	5.69	18	0.316	6.62	0.073
51	1.26	4.75	9	2.24	12.41	0.082
42	1.585	9.96	3	2.57	20.16	0.077
41	5.012	9.09	3	7.58	17.65	0.085
40	3.98	10.52	3	11.75	15.52	0.017

TABLE IIIA

S.R.

Colloid Content = 0.06%

Membrane used MC-3142 and $U_H/U_{Ca} = 1.50$
 $2\text{Humic Acid} + \text{CaCl}_2 \rightarrow \text{Ca}-(\text{Humate})_2 + 2\text{HCl}$.

EMF (mv)	$a_H \times 10^5$	$a_{Ca} \times 10^5$	EMF (mv)	$c_H \times 10^4$	$a_{Ca} \times 10^4$	K	1/k
48	3.162	4.41	29	3.162	5.43	0.81	1.23
50	2.512	3.94	22	3.981	2.00	0.49	2.02
50	2.512	3.94	17	5.012	3.57	0.44	2.27
37	6.31	6.06	5	10.00	10.90	0.14	7.16
49	2.51	4.40	5	6.31	13.17	0.21	4.74
51	2.09	3.81	3.5	6.31	15.91	0.22	4.58

TABLE IIIB

$\text{Ca}-(\text{Humate})_2 + 2\text{HCl} \rightarrow \text{Humic Acid} + \text{CaCl}_2$.

EMF	$a_H \times 10^5$	$a_{Ca} \times 10^5$	EMF	$a_H \times 10^5$	$a_{Ca} \times 10^4$	K
46	0.631	7.91	14	6.31	9.22	0.116
47	0.398	7.31	10	7.08	12.53	0.05
45	0.398	8.54	8	8.91	14.61	0.034
45	0.316	8.54	7	7.94	15.78	0.029
34	1.778	19.88	5	10.00	18.40	0.292
36	1.995	17.03	4	10.00	19.81	0.440

TABLE IVA

SR.
Dehradun

Membrane used—MC-3142 and $U_H/U_{Ba} = 1.00$
 $2\text{Humic Acid} + \text{BaCl}_2 \rightarrow \text{Ba}-(\text{Humate})_2 + 2\text{HCl}$.

Humate phase			Solution phase			K	1/k
E.M.F. read against $a_{Ba} = 0.0027$	$a_H \times 10^5$	$a_{Ba} \times 10^5$	EMF(mv) read against $a_{Ca} = 0.0027$	$a_H \times 10^4$	$a_{Ba} \times 10^4$		
48	2.455	4.05	24	3.548	2.50	33.87	0.030
48	1.995	4.29	18	5.01	8.23	32.84	0.030
46	2.30	6.76	13	5.08	7.45	21.51	0.058
47	2.24	6.19	11	5.012	9.20	33.72	0.030
49	2.951	4.89	8	5.012	12.10	11.66	0.081
47.5	3.09	5.49	7	5.62	12.97	13.99	0.071
49	2.291	5.14	4	5.01	17.35	14.18	0.070

TABLE IVB

E.M.F.	$a_H \times 10^5$	$a_{Ba} \times 10^5$	E.M.F.	$a_H \times 10^4$	$a_{Ba} \times 10^4$	K
70	0.126	1.24	30	0.10	2.50	0.32
51	1.585	4.59	14	1.00	8.72	0.46
50	3.16	4.24	7	4.467	13.55	0.16
48	5.01	4.27	5	7.58	14.60	0.15
52	5.62	2.17	5	10.47	13.15	0.17
41	5.62	8.78	0	19.95	15.03	0.13

TABLE VA

Assam

E.M.F (mv)	$a_H \times 10^8$	$a_{Ca} \times 10^5$	E.M.F (mv)	$a_H \times 10^8$	$a_{Ca} \times 10^4$	K	1/k
45	3.16	6.17	20	2.09	4.25	6.34	0.1517
42	2.82	8.64	15	1.995	7.04	6.151	0.1626
40	3.98	9.52	13	2.09	8.39	3.126	0.32
51	3.09	3.06	10	2.512	10.65	1.90	0.5267
54	3.16	1.91	9	2.754	11.37	1.274	0.7852
57	2.51	1.52	7	2.29	14.06	0.8982	1.113
58	1.99	1.65	5	2.09	16.83	1.075	0.929
59	2.512	1.03	3.5	3.71	18.35	1.225	0.8168

TABLE VB

E.M.F.	$a_H \times 10^5$	$a_{Ca} \times 10^5$	E.M.F.	$a_H \times 10^4$	$a_{Ca} \times 10^4$	K
40	0.0316	12.49	32.20	0.025	2.26	0.028
54	0.166	4.15	9.30	2.82	11.10	0.092
54	1.32	3.29	10.60	6.31	7.23	0.96
55	0.10	3.91	5.60	11.22	9.98	0.002
50	3.16	3.45	2.00	14.13	12.56	0.018
42	5.01	7.00	1.00	17.78	15.81	0.018

TABLE VIA

Assam

Membrane used—MC-3142 and $U_H/U_{Ba} = 1.0$
 $2\text{Humic Acid} + \text{BaCl}_2 \rightarrow \text{Ba}(\text{Humate})_2 + 2\text{HCl}$.

Humate phase			Solution phase			K	1/k
E.M.F (mv)	$a_H \times 10^5$	$a_{Ba} \times 10^5$	E.M.F (mv)	$a_H \times 10^4$	$a_{Ba} \times 10^4$		
45	2.455	7.31	20	2.455	4.59	15.95	0.0627
47	2.455	6.09	15	2.512	7.29	8.758	0.1143
46	1.95	6.93	12	2.95	9.27	16.87	0.0593
47	1.99	6.82	11	2.455	10.47	9.868	0.1014
49	1.778	5.40	8	3.00	13.11	11.70	0.0692
51	1.778	4.48	7	3.02	14.85	8.708	0.1148

TABLE VIB

$\text{Ba}(\text{Humate})_2 + 2\text{HCl} \rightarrow \text{BaCl}_2 + 2\text{HA}$.

E.M.F.	$a_H \times 10^5$	$a_{Ba} \times 10^5$	E.M.F.	$a_H \times 10^4$	$a_{Ba} \times 10^4$	K
45	15.09	0.99	7	5.012	13.27	13.00
41	21.10	1.04	9	6.31	10.38	11.01
36	30.10	1.99	6	7.94	13.06	9.43
41	19.64	1.77	4	12.60	13.56	1.85
39	23.00	2.03	2	15.85	15.24	1.57
40	21.70	1.65	0	19.85	15.03	1.08

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The equilibrium constants K_F and K_B of the system studied from the forward as well as backward directions are given in Tables IA to VA and IB to VB respectively. In the case of normal exchange taking place the K_F should equal $1/K_B$, but the results show considerable discrepancies in all the systems studied.

A similar kind of discrepancy was observed in the case of clay system¹⁰ which was explained by the existence of a phenomena of hysteresis in exchange reactions.

From the values of equilibrium constants it is evident that barium has a much stronger affinity than calcium for the humus. Again values of K_{Ca} and K_{Ba} indicate that hydrogen can not easily replace Ba and Ca from the corresponding salts or expressed differently, the bonding energies of Ba^{+2} and Ca^{+2} ions are greater than the corresponding H^+ ion of humic acids.